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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NEUROSCIENCE AND LITERACY: BRAIN PROCESSES AND EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

AUTHORS

Renata de Araújo Prediger (adelirerenata@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

This study looked at the relationship between neuroscience and literacy, with the aim of understanding the brain processes involved in learning to read and write. Using a literature review approach, relevant studies published in the last ten years were selected. Analysis of the results revealed the importance of phonological skills, the dual pathway model and neural plasticity in this process. The results highlighted the need for teachers to be familiar with neuroscientific knowledge in order to improve their educational practices. Incorporating these contributions can improve academic performance and promote more effective pedagogical strategies in literacy.